

Nuclear Localization of Receptor Tyrosine Kinases in Cancers

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Receptor tyrosine kinases (RTKs) are a major type of cell surface receptors that modulate crucial intracellular signal transduction via extracellular ligand binding. To date, human RTKs consist of 20 subfamilies in which most of them have been considered as therapeutic targets in cancers [1]. For instance, among the ErbB family RTKs, overexpression and/or constitutive activation of EGF receptor (EGFR)/ErbB1, ErbB2, and ErbB3 are frequently observed in many tumors of epithelial origin. All of the ErbB family members, except ErbB4 with an unclear oncogenic role, are well-recognized oncoproteins involved in aggressive cancer behaviors, such as cancer initiation, tumor growth, metastasis, chemotherapeutic resistance, and poor patient survival. Accordingly, two major types of anti-cancer therapy targeting EGFR and ErbB2, ectodomain-binding antibodies (e.g., cetuximab, trastuzumab, ado-trastuzumab emtansine, and pertuzumab) and small-molecule tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs; e.g., erlotinib, gefitinib, and lapatinib), have been developed with promising clinical outcomes, and many of them have been approved by the US Food and Drug Administration.

Interestingly, in addition to their traditional roles in cytoplasmic signaling cascades, 11 classes of RTKs, including subfamilies of ErbB, insulin receptor, PDGF receptor, VEGF receptor, FGF receptor, HGF receptor/cMet, Trk receptor, Ror receptor, Mer receptor, Eph receptor, and Ryk receptor, have been reported to translocate from the cell surface to the nucleus, where they transduced signals to exert the associated biological functions [2,3,4,5,6]. This non-canonical nuclear localization of RTKs and cell surface receptors are termed membrane receptors in the nucleus (MRIN) [7]. Here, we focus on nuclear EGFR, one of the best-characterized RTKs in the MRIN field, and update its clinical/therapeutic impacts, molecular and biological functions, and subcellular trafficking mechanisms.

Nuclear EGFR that exists as a full-length form was first reported in hepatocytes during liver regeneration decades ago. In various tumor tissues, including breast cancer, ovarian cancer, and oropharyngeal and esophageal squamous cell

carcinomas, nuclear EGFR is associated with poor patient outcome. In addition, nuclear expression of EGFRVIII, a constitutively activated EGFR type III variant, is also correlated with poor clinical prognosis in prostate cancer. Furthermore, nuclear EGFR has been shown to be responsible for resistance to various cancer therapies, including radiation and treatments of cisplatin, cetuximab, lapatinib, and gefitinib. Collectively, these findings demonstrate that nuclear localization of EGFR is clinically relevant in multiple cancer types and contributes to resistance to anti-cancer treatments [2].

The molecular and biological functions of nuclear EGFR have been extensively investigated and are mainly involved in transcriptional regulation and signaling transduction related to DNA replication and DNA damage repair [2,8]. Briefly, nuclear EGFR that contains an intrinsic transactivation activity at the carboxyl terminus can function as a transcriptional co-activator to activate target gene promoters, such as *cyclin D1*, *B-Myb*, *iNOS*, *Aurora-A*, *cyclooxygenase-2*, *c-Myc*, *TYMS* (thymidylate synthase), and *BCRP/ABCG2* (breast cancer-resistant protein), through association with transcriptional factors. Nuclear EGFR also acts as a protein kinase to phosphorylate the chromatin-bound proliferative cell nuclear antigen (PCNA), by stabilizing PCNA protein, leading to DNA replication and repair. Most recently, EGFR was shown to enhance phosphorylation of MCM7, a licensing factor critical for DNA replication, through Lyn kinase phosphorylation in human cancers [9]. It would be interesting to further investigate whether nuclear EGFR also plays a role in the MCM7-mediated DNA replication licensing. Moreover, in a ligand-independent manner, DNA damage events and oxidative stress induce protein-protein interaction between nuclear EGFR with DNA-dependent protein kinase (DNAPK), an enzyme that is required for the non-homologous end-joining DNA repair of double-strand breaks, and contribute to DNA repair and chemo- and radio-resistance. Yu et al. further reported an undiscovered mechanism by which nuclear EGFR/DNAPK mediates cell survival that leads to radio-resistance through DNAPK-mediated phosphorylation and inactivation of a newly-identified nuclear EGFR-associated protein,

polynucleotide phosphorylase, an exoribonuclease that regulates the homeostasis of c-Myc mRNA [10]. Together, evidence to date suggests that nuclear EGFR functions as a transcriptional co-activator and a protein kinase modulating multiple biological functions, such as cell proliferation, tumor progression, DNA replication, DNA repair, and resistance to certain anti-cancer treatments.

Abnormal localization and altered compartmentalization of RTKs have also been shown to play a role in the development of various types of cancer. Below, we summarize the subcellular trafficking mechanisms of EGFR. Cell surface EGFR is routed, via endocytosis and endosomal sorting, to either the lysosomes for degradation or the cell surface membrane for recycling. While the mode of EGFR intracellular signaling is being gradually deciphered, current studies indicate that internalized EGFR after endocytosis is transported from the cell surface to a variety of compartments, such as the Golgi apparatus, the endoplasmic reticulum (ER), the mitochondria, as well as the nucleus [2,11]. Most recently, results from our laboratory indicate that EGF-induced Golgi translocation of EGFR from the cell surface is mediated by microtubule through an association with dynein, involving syntaxin 6-dependent fusion with the Golgi membrane [12]. Furthermore, Golgi-to-ER retrograde trafficking regulates EGF-dependent EGFR translocation to the nucleus [13]. Interestingly, cell surface EGFR is targeted to the inner nuclear membrane (INM) of the nuclear envelope (NE) under EGF stimulation via a proposed mechanism termed INTERNET, standing for the integral trafficking from the ER to the NE transport [14,15]. Sequentially, the INM-anchored EGFR is released from the lipid bilayer of INM to the nucleoplasm within the nucleus mediated by an INM-localized Sec61 β translocon that has been traditionally thought to be associated with the ER membrane [15]. In addition to intracellular trafficking of cell surface EGFR, studies have also shown that EGFR is secreted into the exosomes within the extracellular environment in different tumors [16,17]. Since exosomes carrying proteins, mRNAs, and microRNAs can function in intercellular communication involving tumorigenesis, it is worthwhile to further study the potential roles and trafficking mechanisms of exosomal EGFR in cancers.

In summary, multiple human RTKs are known to travel and function at various cellular compartments, including the nucleus. A better understanding of the trafficking mechanisms underlying transportation of cell surface RTKs to different cellular destinations will advance our knowledge of their unique functions and shed light on both the receptor biology and potential therapeutic targets for clinical application as RTKs are implicated in many cancers.

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